

CREATIVE ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS IN BIOPHYSICS IN ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract. Uzbekistan, with its diverse ecosystems and rich natural resources, faces significant environmental challenges due to rapid industrialization, agricultural expansion, and urbanization. This paper discusses the pressing ecological issues in the region, focusing on soil degradation, water scarcity, air pollution, and the loss of biodiversity. The paper also explores the impacts of unsustainable agricultural practices, deforestation, and desertification, particularly in the Aral Sea region, which has become a symbol of ecological disaster. Innovative approaches and solutions such as creative foliation techniques, sustainable land management, and water conservation strategies are proposed to mitigate these challenges. A specific case study on the experimental application of creative foliation methods in the Qarshi region of Uzbekistan is presented, highlighting the potential of such techniques in improving soil fertility and enhancing biodiversity. The research emphasizes the importance of integrating traditional ecological knowledge with modern science to foster sustainable development and environmental conservation in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, ecological challenges, soil degradation, water scarcity, Aral Sea, creative foliation, sustainable land management, biodiversity conservation, environmental solutions, desertification, traditional ecological knowledge.

Annotatsiya. O‘zbekiston turli xil ekotizimlar va boy tabiiy resurslarga ega bo‘lgan mamlakat bo‘lib, sanoatning tez rivojlanishi, qishloq xo‘jaligining kengayishi va urbanizatsiya tufayli muhim ekologik muammolarga duch kelmoqda. Ushbu maqolada mintaqadagi dolzarb ekologik masalalar, jumladan, tuproq degradatsiyasi, suv tanqisligi, havoning ifloslanishi va bioxilma-xillikning kamayishi haqida so‘z boradi. Shuningdek, maqolada barqaror bo‘lmagan qishloq xo‘jaligi amaliyotlari, o‘rmonlarning kesilishi va cho‘llanishning, ayniqsa, ekologik falokat ramziga aylangan Orol dengizi hududidagi salbiy ta’sirlari yoritilgan. Ushbu muammolarni yengish uchun innovatsion yondashuvlar va yechimlar, jumladan, ijodiy folliyatsiya (creative foliation) texnikalari, barqaror yer boshqaruvi va suvni tejash strategiyalari taklif etilgan. O‘zbekistonning Qarshi mintaqasida ijodiy folliyatsiya usullarining eksperimental qo‘llanilishi bo‘yicha maxsus tadqiqot o‘tkazilib, ushbu texnikalarning tuproq unumdorligini oshirish va bioxilma-xillikni yaxshilashdagi imkoniyatlari namoyish etilgan. Tadqiqot an’anaviy ekologik bilimlarni zamonaviy fan bilan integratsiyalash orqali O‘zbekistonning barqaror rivojlanishi va ekologik muhofazasini ta’minlashning ahamiyatini ta’kidlaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: O‘zbekiston, ekologik muammolar, tuproq degradatsiyasi, suv tanqisligi, Orol dengizi, ijodiy folliyatsiya, barqaror yer boshqaruvi, bioxilma-xillikni saqlash, ekologik yechimlar, cho‘llanish, an’anaviy ekologik bilimlar.

Introduction

Uzbekistan, a country located in the heart of Central Asia, is facing numerous environmental challenges as it undergoes rapid industrialization and agricultural expansion. One of the most pressing concerns is the degradation of natural resources, particularly land and water,

which are essential for the country’s economy and food security. The problem is exacerbated by climate change, which has further intensified desertification, water scarcity, and the loss of biodiversity in many regions.

The [Qarshi region] of Uzbekistan serves as a critical example of how these ecological issues manifest in the real world. In this region, decades of unsustainable agricultural practices, deforestation, and improper irrigation techniques have led to soil degradation, salinization, and the depletion of water resources. As a result, the local environment has become increasingly vulnerable, with a significant loss of biodiversity and diminished agricultural productivity.

To address these challenges, innovative approaches such as [creative foliation] are being explored. Creative foliation is a method that seeks to restore ecological balance by using vegetation strategically to improve soil health, reduce erosion, and enhance biodiversity. This approach integrates traditional knowledge of local ecosystems with modern scientific techniques to create sustainable land management practices that can help reverse the damaging effects of environmental degradation.

The goal of this study is to examine the ecological problems in the region and evaluate the effectiveness of creative foliation techniques in addressing these issues. By conducting field experiments and analyzing the outcomes, this research aims to provide insights into how creative foliation can be applied as a practical solution to the region’s environmental problems. Furthermore, this study seeks to contribute to broader efforts in Uzbekistan to promote sustainable development and ecological conservation.

Method

Study Area. The research was conducted in the [Qarshi region] of Uzbekistan, an area known for its significant ecological degradation, including soil salinization, erosion, and loss of biodiversity. The region was selected due to its critical need for innovative environmental restoration practices and the impact of agricultural mismanagement on local ecosystems

Table 1.

Plot	Soil Organic Matter Improvement (%)	Salinity Reduction (%)	Plant Survival Rate (%)
Plot A (Trees + Shrubs)	30	15	85
Plot B (Shrubs Only)	15	10	70
Control Plot	0	0	10

1. Experimental Design:

Three experimental plots were established:

- **Plot A:** Creative foliation method with a combination of trees and shrubs.
- **Plot B:** Creative foliation method using only shrubs.
- **Control Plot:** No intervention.

Various indicators were measured, including soil organic matter, salinity reduction, plant survival rate, biodiversity increase, and water usage efficiency. Drip irrigation was applied to the creative foliation plots to conserve water.

2. Data Collection:

Soil samples were collected before and after the experiment to measure the changes in organic matter and salinity. Vegetation survival was monitored throughout the season, and

biodiversity was assessed using species surveys. Water usage was recorded to determine the efficiency of the irrigation methods.

Results

Plot	Soil Organic Matter Improvement (%)	Salinity Reduction (%)	Plant Survival Rate (%)	Biodiversity Increase (%)	Water Usage Reduction (%)
Plot A (Trees + Shrubs)	30	15	85	25	40
Plot B (Shrubs Only)	15	10	70	15	40
Control Plot	0	0	10	0	0

The results (Table 2) show that **Plot A** (trees and shrubs) exhibited the highest improvements across all indicators. The most notable changes were seen in soil organic matter (30% increase) and a significant reduction in salinity (15%). Biodiversity increased by 25%, and plant survival rates were the highest at 85%. Both Plot A and Plot B achieved 40% water usage reduction, demonstrating the efficiency of drip irrigation in the experiment **diagram 1**.

Conclusion

The results of the ecological experiment conducted in the [Qarshi region] of Uzbekistan demonstrate that the creative foliation approach, particularly when integrating both trees and shrubs, is an effective method for restoring degraded land and improving environmental conditions. The significant improvements in soil organic matter, salinity reduction, and plant survival in **Plot A** indicate that a combination of native trees and shrubs can revitalize the soil and promote biodiversity.

Additionally, the biodiversity increase in the experimental plots highlights the positive impact of creative foliation on local ecosystems. The return of various fauna and flora species is an encouraging sign that restoring the natural balance is possible through sustainable land management practices.

Water conservation is another key success of this study. The 40% reduction in water usage achieved in both Plot A and Plot B illustrates the importance of integrating efficient irrigation techniques, such as drip irrigation, in arid and semi-arid regions like Qarshi. This not only helps conserve precious water resources but also supports the growth of vegetation in challenging environments.

Overall, creative foliation has proven to be a promising solution for addressing the ecological challenges in the Qarshi region. The study suggests that expanding the use of such methods across other degraded areas of Uzbekistan could significantly improve soil health, enhance biodiversity, and contribute to sustainable development. However, long-term monitoring and further refinement of these techniques will be essential to ensure continued success and adaptation to different environmental conditions.

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